

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 141

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 141

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 141:0 A Psalm of David.</p>	
<p>Psa. 141:1 O LORD, I call upon You; ^ahasten to me! ^bGive ear to my voice when I call to You! ² May my prayer be ¹counted as ^aincense before You; The ^blifting up of my hands as the ^cevening offering. ³ Set a ^aguard, O LORD, ¹over my mouth; Keep watch over the ^bdoor of my lips. ⁴ ^aDo not incline my heart to any evil thing, To practice deeds ¹of wickedness With men who ^bdo iniquity; And ^cdo not let me eat of their delicacies.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 141:1 מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד יְהוָה קְרָאתִיךָ תוֹשָׁה לִי הִאֲזִינָה קוֹלִי בְקִרְאֵי־לְךָ : ² תִּפְּזוֹן תִּפְּלְתִי קִטְרֹת לְפָנֶיךָ מִשָּׂאת כַּפֵּי מִנְחַת־עָרֵב : ³ שִׁיתָה יְהוָה שְׁמִרָה לְפִי נִצְרָה עַל־דַּל שְׂפָתַי : ⁴ אֶל־תִּט־לִבִּי לְדַבָּר וְלֹעַ לְהִתְעוֹלֵל עַל־לוֹת וּבְרָשַׁע אֶת־אִישִׁים פַּעַל־אֵוֶן וּבַל־אֶלְחָם בְּמַנְעֻמֵיהֶם : ⁵ יְהִלְמֵנִי צְדִיק אֲחֹסֶד וַיּוֹכִיחֵנִי שֹׁמֵן רֹאשׁ אֶל־יְגִי רֹאשֵׁי כִי־עוֹד וְתִפְּלְתִי בְרַעוּתֵיהֶם : ⁶ נִשְׁמָטוּ בִידֵי־סֹלַע שְׂפָטֵיהֶם וְשָׂמְעוּ אִמְרֵי כִי נִעְמּוּ : ⁷ כָּמוֹ פֶלֶחַ וּבִקְעָה בְּאַרְצָן נִפְזָרוּ עֲצָמֵינוּ לְפִי שְׂאוֹל : ⁸ כִּי אֶלֶיךָ יְהוָה אֲדַבְּרֵנִי עֵינַי בְּכַה חֲסִיתִי אֶל־תִּעַר נַפְשִׁי : ⁹ שְׁמֹרֵנִי מִיַּד פֶּחַ נִקְשׁוּ לִי וּמִקְשׁוֹת פַּעַל־לִי אֵוֶן : ¹⁰ יִפְּלוּ בְּמַכְמַרְיוֹ רַשָּׁעִים יַחַד אֲנֹכִי עַד־אֶעְבֹּר :</p>
<p>Psa. 141:5 Let the ^arighteous smite me ¹in kindness and reprove me; It is ^boil upon the head; Do not let my head refuse it, ²For still my prayer ^cis ³against their wicked deeds. ⁶ Their judges are ^athrown down by the sides of the rock, And they hear my words, for they are pleasant. ⁷ As when one ^aplows and breaks open the earth, Our ^bbones have been scattered at the ^cmouth of ¹Sheol.</p>	

Psa. 141:8 For my ^aeyes are toward
You, O ¹GOD, the Lord;

In You I ^btake refuge; ^cdo not
²leave me defenseless.

⁹ Keep me from the ^{1a}jaws of the
trap which they have set for me,

And from the ^bsnares of those who
do iniquity.

¹⁰ Let the wicked ^afall into their own
nets,

While I pass by ^{1b}safely.

References

Psalm 141:1

^aPs 22:19; 38:22; 70:5

^bPs 5:1; 143:1

Psalm 141:2

¹Lit *fixed*

^aEx 30:8; Luke 1:10; Rev 5:8; 8:3, 4

^{b1} Tim 2:8

^cEx 29:39, 41; 1 Kin 18:29, 36; Dan 9:21

Psalm 141:3

¹Lit *to*

^aPs 34:13; 39:1; Prov 13:3; 21:23

^bMic 7:5

Psalm 141:4

¹Lit *in*

^aPs 119:36

^bIs 32:6; Hos 6:8; Mal 3:15

^cProv 23:6

Psalm 141:5

¹Or *lovingly*

²Lit *And my prayer*

³Or *in spite of their calamities*

^aProv 9:8; 19:25; 25:12; 27:6; Eccl 7:5; Gal 6:1

^bPs 23:5; 133:2

^cPs 35:14

Psalm 141:6

^{a2} Chr 25:12

Psalm 141:7

¹I.e. the nether world

^aPs 129:3

^bPs 53:5

^cNum 16:32, 33; Ps 88:3-5

Psalm 141:8

¹Heb *YHWH*, usually rendered *LORD*

²Lit *pour out my soul*

^aPs 25:15; 123:2

^bPs 2:12; 11:1

^cPs 27:9

Psalm 141:9

¹Lit *bands of the trap*

^aPs 38:12; 64:5; 91:3; 119:110

^bPs 140:5

Psalm 141:10

¹Lit *altogether*

^aPs 7:15; 35:8; 57:6

^bPs 124:7

Targum

Psa. 141:1 A psalm of David. O LORD, I have called you; be concerned for me, hear my voice when I call to you. ² Let my prayer be directed before you like incense of spices, the upraising of my hands in prayer like a fragrant gift offered at evening. ³ Place, O LORD, a guard on my mouth, a keeper on the portal of my lips. ⁴ Do not incline my heart to anything evil, to think thoughts in wickedness to join with men who practice deceit, and I will not dine at the revels of their banquets. ⁵ The righteous man will strike me because of kindness, and rebuke me; the oil of holy anointing will not cease from my head, for still my prayer is marshaled against their evil. ⁶ They have withdrawn from the academy because of their harsh judgments; they turn and hear my words, for they are pleasant. ⁷ For like a man who labors and cleaves when plowing the earth, so are our limbs scattered on the mouth of the grave. ⁸ Therefore, unto you, God, the LORD, do my eyes look; I have hoped in your word, do not empty out my soul. ⁹ Protect me from the power of the trap they have hidden for me, and the snares of those who practice deceit. ¹⁰ May the wicked men fall into his nets together, until the time that I pass by.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

King David composed this Psalm as he fled from Saul. David knew that Saul's anger was created by slanders people offered about David. He pleaded to the LORD for protection from the people chasing him and slandering him.

Notes on this Psalm

When something goes wrong in your life do you turn to the LORD for help? David certainly did all his life. Sometimes just talking to the LORD about your situation will help you solve it. The solution may come to you subconsciously. The Shekinah is with every person. Therefore, the Shekinah can influence a person to turn left or right. Never underestimate the power of the LORD through the Shekinah.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

